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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10069119>**Abstract**

The European integration process has become a reality. The prospect of expansion together with the deepening of relations between non-member countries is no longer a dream, but a challenge. The growing awareness of the political majority, the academic world and public opinion to be involved in the processes of establishing a more complete institutional Europe, based on its intellectual, cultural, social, scientific and technological dimensions, poses major tasks to education.

The Europe of knowledge is already widely accepted as a pan-European objective, as an irreplaceable factor for increasing human capacities, for the enrichment and consolidation of European citizenship. The importance of education and educational cooperation in the development and strengthening of stable, peaceful and democratic societies is universally recognized as essential. Nowadays in Albania, but not only, the entire system of higher education has been put under the pressure of changes in the framework of changes and transformations that the entire human society is undergoing in the framework of "globalization". Today the guiding motto of the CoE "learning by doing"²⁹ has been turned into "doing by learning". Changes are interactive: Achievements transform not only reality but also man. Many today face the challenge of achieving goals without having a role model. Many face the obligation to be creative, reflective and flexible in the process of change.

Introduction

Why and should the foreign language teaching system change today?

It is known that universities and educational institutions are generally "change-averse"³⁰(against changes), but many, without thinking too much, would say that it is a must. The answer is simple, but the problem behind it is quite complex and complicated. To help the reform of higher education, a European-wide initiative was found that bears the name of a city, which has a tradition of higher education for centuries - the Bologna Charter or Process. The Bologna Charter³¹, which was also adopted by the Albanian state, is an instrument of reform or adaptation for universities. The Charter of Bologna is a continuation of the "Magna Charta", a 1988 document signed on the occasion of the celebration of the ninth century of the founding of the University of Bologna. The Bologna Charter is a guiding document on the nature of change: will universities change globally (all according to one scheme), or will they respect particularities? As well as on the attitude that should be maintained towards the tradition of learning: will it be discarded or will it remain the basis of changes?

Results and discussion

Faced with the dilemmas of change, it goes without saying that the answer is no longer so "simple". The more traditions the institution of higher education has, the more difficult the change is. The context of change is also compromised by the domestic external factor.

The academic and research community is not only faced with the challenge of what to do with the experience created, but also with challenges such as:

- The changing of national environment

The financial pressure, the increase in competition, the variety of forms of learning are always more sensitive in the internal environment.

- Increasing institutional autonomy

The role, its nature, organization, good governance are dilemmas of many institutions that seek to improve.

- Organization and renewal of educational curricula

The curriculum of pre-university education has been reformed and is expected more and more in the university curriculum. Learning achievements, credits, traditional learning, "distance learning", "life long learning", are no longer evasive concepts, but living practices in many higher schools.

- Internet and new technologies

New ways of communication and learning are much more alive and expect to be allies of daily teaching in school environments. The increase in the level of technologies in the labor market in Europe will continue to increase its pressure in the Albanian labor market, to which the Albanian Higher Education must make its contribution.

- Intensification of European integration processes

In a Europe without geographical borders, the education of society occupies a special role. The necessity

²⁹ Birdwell J., Scott R., Koninckx D., 2015, Learning by Doing, <https://www.academia.edu/30154518/>

³⁰ Fullan M., Scott G., Jossey-Bass, 2009, Turnaround Leadership for Higher Education, 170 pp, San Francisco.

³¹ The Bologna Process is an intergovernmental higher education reform process that includes 49 European countries and a number of European organisations, including EUA. Its main purpose is to enhance the quality and recognition of European higher education systems and to improve the conditions for exchange and collaboration within Europe, as well as internationally, <https://eua.eu/issues/10:bologna-process.html>

of the identification of the information measurement system makes the integration imperative. Respect for diversity and the chance of integration are related to it.

- Internationalization of the labor market

The compatibility and comparison of education and scientific research systems dictates the sameness of the reference system, the creation of a European space of Higher Education.

- Open commitment to ensure quality in education

The Bologna Process has brought us a long way towards achieving the goals for European higher education set two decades ago. This third edition of the Bologna Process Implementation Report provides clear

evidence of change in the higher education landscape. It shows where progress has been made, but also points to the gaps that need to be filled if we are to strengthen European higher education cooperation on the basis of quality and mutual trust³². Increasing the quality of professional training requires confronting the labor market.

- It is time for pragmatism

Finally, the problem is posed from a pragmatic point of view. Should society continue to spend financial and human resources to train specialists who will probably never work as scientific researchers, but only as project managers or directly in production? The duty of higher education institutions to respond to the demands of the labor market, for the different levels of qualification, is imperative. In the framework of efficiency in the time frames and commitments above, the issue of learning the foreign language of the profession faster and more qualitatively is raised. It definitely constitutes a required dimension of the graduate in the framework of the needs for European integration. Should the foreign language teaching curriculum be improved at the Polytechnic University, now that the Ministry of Education and Science has made English official as the first foreign language. Is it worth keeping the English language in universities where the curriculum is not very different from that of high school?

What are the benefits of this changes and how are they reflected in language learning?

The university has a solid structure that is difficult to redimension in accordance with the economic and technological changes of the time. The current problems that concern Albanian Universities in the field today, without pretending that they are the only and permanent ones, we list.

- Fragmented institutional infrastructure
- Senior research staff
- Incoherent research policy
- Lack of funds
- Lack of medium-term strategy and entrepreneurial mentality.

The improvement of foreign language teaching will make the results of the reform more visible in many directions. Students and lecturers will be more integrated in the field of university research. Scientific research requires new dimensions of understanding the idea of building a European research area. Today students and lecturers are challenged by the ideas of a

global research market and the need to create new knowledge and ideas. The different national structures of scientific research must find their optimal ways to be included in the European Research Area. The mastery of a foreign language in the applied academic aspect is no longer a matter for discussion.

Assessing that the intensity of scientific research in the country is very small compared to other EU countries, it is imperative to reorient the programs of this research and master communication skills.

The fact that Albania has stabilized macro-economic conditions, the positive development of the banking sector and the functioning of the market economy, require a desired partner for increasing positive results in international programs.

The tasks that must be solved by research policy instruments are:

- Promotion of an institutional research network inside and outside the country;
- Supporting successful participation in EU research programs and international cooperation initiatives;
- Renewal of regional research cooperation; dictate the emergency restructuring of foreign language teaching in higher schools.

European structures and policies see cooperation in the fields of research and education as a stable foundation for building a sustainable economic cooperation, as a favorable environment and prerequisite for further development of mutual interest. Regional cooperation strengthens sustainable development and plays an important role for prosperity.

The intensity of the European interaction of today and the future dictates improvements in daily and scientific communication habits.

The main criteria for active interaction between European factors are:

- Qualitative research;
- Wide impact;
- Exchange of information;

Conclusions

What are the main benefits of improving foreign language communication skills of students and newly graduated specialists?

- Preparation for an efficient participation in major EU programs;
- Solving sensitive problems of the region (environment, health, infrastructure);
- Importing the European tradition for the development of scientific research;
- Rapid spread of knowledge and information
- Creating a good foundation for modern education activities through scientific research.

These are some of the needs for more cooperation in the region and Europe that dictate the mastery of a foreign language instrument. The most important factor to evaluate the quality of university products today is the employment index for a graduate, formed by a particular program, institution or university anywhere in

³² European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2018. The European Higher Education Area in 2018: Bologna Process

Implementation Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Europe. To determine the employment indicator, the main factors can be taken into consideration.

One thing is clear for European institutions: a state that invests in education and science is a state that belongs to the future.

The tasks facing the high school in the preparation of graduates according to the employment index are challenging and the mastery of a foreign language instrument remains a prerequisite for achievement.

References:

1. Birdwell J., Scott R., Koninckx D., 2015, Learning by Doing, <https://www.academia.edu/30154518/>

2. Fullan M., Scott G., Jossey-Bass, 2009, Turn-around Leadership for Higher Education, 170 pp, San Francisco.

3. The Bologna Process is an intergovernmental higher education reform process that includes 49 European countries and a number of European organisations, including EUA. Its main purpose is to enhance the quality and recognition of European higher education systems and to improve the conditions for exchange and collaboration within Europe, as well as internationally, <https://eua.eu/issues/10:bologna-process.html>

4. European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2018. The European Higher Education Area in 2018: Bologna Process Implementation Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.